

Studies on Formazans : Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-3-[α -(*p*-arsenophenyl/phenylazo)-substituted-benzalamino]indole

B. H. TRIVEDI and V. H. SHAH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005

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The titled derivatives have been synthesised by the reaction of 2-phenyl-3-aminoindole with different aromatic aldehydes to yield Schiff bases. These Schiff bases are treated with diazotised aromatic amines at lower temperature. The compounds have been screened for antimicrobial activity.

Indole and its derivatives possess a wide spectrum of biological activity¹. It is reported that formazans² exhibit insecticidal, bactericidal and antiviral properties. In view of these findings, the present paper reports the synthesis of fiftyone compounds wherein 2-phenyl-3-substituted-benzalaminoindoles and formazans have been combined so as to have molecules of enhanced overall biological activity. The monoheterocycle and its precursor were screened for the biological activity.

2-Phenyl-3-aminoindole³ was obtained by nitration of 2-phenylindole followed by alkaline dithionite reduction. The aminoindole (1) when treated with different aromatic aldehydes yielded 2-phenyl-3-substituted-benzalaminoindole (2) followed by the reaction with diazotised aromatic amines to yield 2-phenyl-3-[α -(*p*-arsenophenyl/phenylazo)substituted-benzalamino]indole (3) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu DT-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Hitachi spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D-350 instrument. The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3-(*p*)-methoxybenzalaminoindole (2): A mixture of 2-phenyl-3-aminoindole (0.01 mol) and *p*-anisaldehyde (0.01 mol) in dry methanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol-dioxane (3 : 1), (71%), m.p. 139° (Found : C, 80.91 ; N, 5.49 ; H, 8.61. C₁₈H₁₅N₂O requires : C, 80.98 ; H, 5.52 ; N, 8.58% ; ν_{\max} 1360 (C-N amine), 1410, 1510, 1575, 1605 (-C=C ring str. aromatic), 1630 (N=CH-R Schiff base), 1650 (NH indole) and 3050 cm⁻¹ (=C-H aromatic multiple bands) ; δ 3.71 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.05 (1H, s, -N=CH), 6.97-7.99 (13H, m, ArH) and 9.99 (1H, s, NH in ring) ; m/z 326, 355 (M⁺) (100%), 219, 193, 179, 135, 133 and 77.

R=R'=Aryl
Scheme 1

2-Phenyl-3-[α -phenylazo)-(p)-methoxy benzalamino]indole (3): The previously diazotised aniline solution (0.01 mol) was added with stirring to the cooled solution of 2-phenyl-3-*p*-methoxybenzalaminoindole (0.01 mol) in pyridine (10 ml). The contents were allowed to stand for 48 h at room temperature. The product was isolated and purified through alumina column using chloroform as eluant,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	82	105
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	79	131
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	75	151
4.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	80	218
5.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	79	85
6.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	74	150
7.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	69	93
8.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	60	139
9.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	80	144
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	73	173
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	71	139
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	79	117
13.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	64	102
14.	2-Nitrophenyl	79	125
15.	3-Nitrophenyl	65	206
16.	4-Nitrophenyl	70	243
17.	9-Anthryl	77	229

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.**	R	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	59	99
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	62	95
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	67	155
4.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	57	279
5.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	73	275
6.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	59	173
7.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	61	300
8.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	65	101
9.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	59	99
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	71	109
11.	4-Methoxyphenyl	55	199
12.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	69	205
13.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	64	111
14.	2-Nitrophenyl	68	117
15.	3-Nitrophenyl	71	157
16.	4-Nitrophenyl	63	143
17.	9-Anthryl	67	191
18.	Phenyl	65	161
19.	2-Chlorophenyl	58	117
20.	4-Chlorophenyl	60	157
21.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	59	151
22.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	59	139
23.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	71	110
24.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	70	100
25.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	69	200
26.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	61	103
27.	2-Methoxyphenyl	73	195
28.	4-Methoxyphenyl	70	111
29.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	67	103
30.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	61	201
31.	2-Nitrophenyl	61	108
32.	3-Nitrophenyl	62	115
33.	4-Nitrophenyl	57	111
34.	9-Anthryl	55	201

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**For compounds sl. nos. 1-17, R'≡p-arsenophenyl; for sl. nos. 18-34, R'≡phenyl.

(70%), m.p. 110° (Found: C, 78.18; H, 5.15; N, 13.05. C₂₃H₂₂N₄O requires: C, 78.13; H, 5.11; N, 13.02%); ν_{\max} 1620 (N=N), 1655 (NH indole) and 3150 cm⁻¹ (=C-H), δ 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃) 7.01-8.05 (13H, m, ArH) and 9.98 (1H, s, -NH- in ring); m/z 430, 429 (M⁺) (100%), 353 and 323.

Antimicrobial activity: All the compounds (2 and 3) were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. pyogens* (gram-positive), *E. coli*, *K. arogens* (gram-negative) and for antifungal activity against *A. niger* by cup-plate⁴ method at 50 μ g level using DMF as solvent. After 24 h of incubation at 37°, the zone of inhibition was measured (mm). The activity was compared with ampicillin (*S. aureus* 22; *S. pyogens* 20; *E. coli* 19; *K. arogens* 24), chloramphenicol (*S. aureus* 28; *S. pyogens* 23; *E. coli* 21; *K. arogens* 18), and norfloxacin (*S. aureus* 21; *S. pyogens* 27; *E. coli* 25; *K. arogens* 15) for antibacterial activity and with griseofulvin (*A. niger* 24) for antifungal activity. The activity data is recorded in Tables 1, 2.

In the case of antibacterial activity, the compounds 2 showed activity when R=phenyl (18 mm), 2,4-dichlorophenyl (19), 3,4-dichlorophenyl (18), 4-hydroxyphenyl (18), 4-methoxyphenyl (19), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (20), 2,3-dinitrophenyl (18) against *S. aureus*; when R=4-chlorophenyl (19), 2,6-, 3,4-dichlorophenyl (18), 2-methoxyphenyl (19), 4-methoxyphenyl (18), 4-nitrophenyl (18) against *S. pyogens*; and when R=2,6-dichlorophenyl (19), 3,4-dichlorophenyl (18) against *E. coli*; when R=2-methoxyphenyl (18), 4-nitrophenyl (19) against *K. arogens*. All compounds (2) showed antifungal activity against *A. niger* (10-18 mm).

The antibacterial activity (4-18 mm) and antifungal activity (10-18 mm) of compounds 3 were less against each strain of bacteria and fungi when compared with the activity of the antibacterial activity (10-20 mm) and antifungal activity (10-18 mm).

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